

A NEW COLORIMETRIC METHOD FOR THE ESTIMATION OF LACTOSE IN MILK

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A new colorimetric method for the determination of lactose in milk has been described basing on the reducing properties of lactose under suitable condition. It was observed that when a ferric chloride solution was added to an excess of lactose in alkaline medium containing sodium carbonate and the mixture heated on a water-bath, the ferric iron was completely reduced by lactose.

Reducing properties of lactose have been utilised for the quantitative estimation of this sugar by well-known methods. Recently a colorimetric method has been developed by Tul'chinskii¹, on the basis of reduction by lactose of Cr^{6+} to Cr^{3+} . In order to find out a more rapid and easier colorimetric method, attention of the author was directed to ferric iron. In a preliminary experiment, it was observed that when ferric chloride solution was added to an excess of pure lactose solution in alkaline medium containing sodium carbonate, and the mixture heated on a water-bath for about 15 minutes, the ferric iron was completely reduced.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard ferric chloride solution was prepared by dissolving 0.1 g. of pure iron wire in 5 ml. of hot dilute HCl ; to it was added 0.25 g. of KClO_3 and boiled until free from the odour of chlorine. It was then diluted to 1 litre with distilled water in a volumetric flask (1 ml. $\equiv$ 0.1 mg. ferric iron).

Standard lactose solution was prepared by dissolving 5 g. of pure lactose* in distilled water and diluting it to 1 litre in a volumetric flask (1 ml. $\equiv$ 5 mg. of lactose).

Standard sodium carbonate solution was prepared by dissolving 20 g. of pure anhydrous sodium carbonate in distilled water and making up to 1 litre (1 ml. $\equiv$ 20 mg. of Na_2CO_3).

Ammonium thiocyanate solution was prepared by dissolving 50 g. of pure ammonium thiocyanate crystals in 100 ml. of distilled water.

Lactose in this work stands for hydrated lactose.

Effect of different concentrations of the sodium carbonate solution on the reducing action of lactose.—Into each of 14 test tubes (capacity, 30 ml. approx.) standard lactose solution (2 ml.) was introduced, followed by 5 ml. of the ferric chloride solution. Excepting the first test tube, to each of the rest increasing quantities of the standard sodium carbonate solution were added, starting with 0.25 ml. in the second tube and increasing the dose by the same amount in the successive ones, until in the last tube 3.25 ml. had been added. To each of the 14 tubes requisite amounts of distilled water were then added to make the final volume 20 ml. in each case. All the tubes were kept in a boiling water-bath for 25 minutes. After this period the test tubes were removed from the water-bath, the solution acidified with 0.5 ml. of HCl (conc.) and the unreduced ferric iron was estimated colorimetrically by the thiocyanate method². In applying the thiocyanate method, both the 'test' and the 'standard' were diluted to 50 ml. mark with distilled water in Nessler cylinders, 2 ml. of the ammonium thiocyanate solution was added and the colour compared visually. Results are represented graphically in Fig. 1.

It will be observed that under the above stated condition of the experiment, the amount of ferric iron reduced by a constant amount of the lactose solution increases with increasing concentrations of the sodium carbonate solution up to a certain limit, *i.e.* 2.5 ml. of the latter, beyond which the amount of ferric iron reduced remains constant. Therefore, the minimum amount of the sodium carbonate solution which should be present in a total volume of 20 ml. is 2.5 ml. For all subsequent experiments 3 ml. of the alkali was used.

FIG. 1

Effect of different periods of heating on the reducing action of lactose.—Into each of 8 test tubes 2 ml. of the lactose solution, 5 ml. of the ferric chloride solution

and 3 ml. of the sodium carbonate solution were introduced, followed by 10 ml. of distilled water to make the total volume 20 ml. The ferric iron content of the first tube was determined immediately by the procedure already mentioned. The remaining seven tubes were placed in a boiling water-bath; one tube was taken out every 5 minutes and the ferric iron remaining was determined after acidifying the mixture with 0.5 ml. of HCl (conc.) in the usual manner. Thus, the last tube would have been removed from the water-bath after heating for 35 minutes. Results are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Duration of heating (min.)	0	5	10	15	20	25	30	35
No. of ml. of FeCl_3 soln. reduced by 2 ml. of lactose	0.0	2.0	3.5	4.0	4.1	4.1	4.1	4.1

It will be seen that the iron reduced reaches its maximum after 20 minutes of heating and remains constant thereafter. Therefore, a heating time of 25 minutes may safely be accepted.

Linear relation between the iron reduced and the lactose present in the solution.—Into each of 9 test tubes, 5 ml. of the ferric chloride solution was taken. Excepting the first one into which no lactose solution should be introduced, increasing quantities of the lactose solution were added, starting with 0.25 ml. in the second tube and raising the dose by the same amount in each step, until in the last tube 2.0 ml. was taken. To each, 3 ml. of the sodium carbonate solution was added, followed by requisite quantities of distilled water to bring the volume to 20 ml. All the 9 test tubes were heated in boiling water-bath for 25 minutes, and the unreduced ferric iron was estimated in the usual manner, after acidification with 0.5 ml. of HCl (conc.). From this the volume of ferric chloride solution reduced by the different concentrations of lactose was obtained merely by subtraction.

It would be observed by drawing a graph that almost a perfectly linear relationship exists between the amounts of ferric iron reduced and the lactose present under the conditions of the experiment. The volume of ferric chloride solution which is reduced by 1 ml. of lactose solution, that is, the lactose equivalent of iron, can be accurately calculated, as shown below.

TABLE II

Lactose soln. added.	Ferric chloride soln. reduced.	Ferric chloride soln. reduced by 1 ml. of lactose soln.
0.25 ml.	0.5 ml.	2.0
0.50	1.0	2.0
0.75	1.6	2.13
1.00	2.1	2.1
1.25	2.5	2.0
1.50	3.1	2.07
1.75	3.5	2.0
2.00	4.2	2.1

Simple mean = 2.05

Therefore 1 ml. of the lactose solution reduces 2.05 ml. of the ferric chloride solution.

Procedure for determining lactose in milk.—In applying this method to milk, it is necessary to obtain a perfectly clear milk serum, otherwise correct matching of colour will be impossible. The following procedure was followed for the purpose.

A well-mixed sample of 10 g. was taken into a 250 ml. volumetric flask, diluted to 200 ml. with distilled water and placed on a water-bath. When the diluted sample became warm, 1 ml. of 10% acetic acid solution was added, mixed well and left on the water-bath for at least half an hour for the proteins to coagulate. It was then cooled and made up to mark with distilled water, mixed and filtered through a double dry filter into a dry flask. If the filtrate coming through appears turbid, it is to be passed again through the same filter. In this way a perfectly clear filtrate, almost as clear as distilled water, will be obtained (in the author's laboratory this simple method of clarification is being constantly followed with conspicuous success). The milk serum was tested for the presence of any ferric iron by the thiocyanate solution; a negative result was obtained showing the absence of ferric iron in the filtrate.

The clear milk serum (5 ml.) was pipetted into a test tube, followed by 5 ml. of the ferric chloride solution and by 3 ml. of the sodium carbonate solution, and then by 7 ml. of distilled water to make the volume 20 ml. The contents were heated in a boiling water-bath for 25 minutes, and the ferric iron left was estimated by the usual thiocyanate method after acidifying the mixture with 0.5 ml. of HCl (conc.)

The volume of the ferric chloride solution left was deducted from the total volume taken to obtain the number of ml. of ferric chloride solution reduced by the lactose, and the % lactose in the sample was calculated from the following formula :

Lactose % in sample = $a \times 1.22$, 'a' being the number of ml. of the ferric chloride solution reduced.

Lactose contents of different milk samples determined by the present method were compared with those obtained by the well-known Fehling volumetric method³. A few of the results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Sample No.	Lactose per cent (w/w).		Deviation from Fehling's method.	
	Fehling's method.	Authors' method.	Diff.	Per cent.
1	4.54	4.76	+ 0.22	+ 4.8
2	4.58	4.82	+ 0.24	+ 5.2
3	4.20	4.39	+ 0.19	+ 4.5
4	3.52	3.66	+ 0.14	+ 4.0
5	4.85	5.08	+ 0.23	+ 4.7
6	2.55	2.68	+ 0.13	+ 5.1
7	5.0	5.25	+ 0.25	+ 5.0

TABLE IV

Comparative figures of lactose contents of pure lactose solutions obtained by the authors' and the Fehling method.

Lactose soln. prepared in laboratory.	% Lactose found		Deviation from Fehling's method.	
	Fehling method.	volumetric Author's method.	Difference.	Per cent.
5.0%	5.0	5.05	+ 0.05	+ 1.0
3.5	3.49	3.53	+ 0.04	+ 1.1
4.5	4.48	4.52	+ 0.05	+ 1.1

From the above figures, it will be observed that the agreement between the present and the Fehling method is good when analysing pure lactose solution. But, in estimating lactose in milk, the results obtained by the present method are slightly higher (4 to 5%) than by the Fehling method. However, the method being quite simple and rapid is readily adaptable in routine analysis and serves as an alternative to other well-known methods.

R E F E R E N C E S

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3. Cox, "The Chemical Analysis of Foods", Churchill, London, 3rd. Ed., 1946, p. 231.